

Spectrophotometric Determination of Copper, Rhodium, Palladium and Platinum with 4-S-Benzyl-1-Parachlorophenyl-5-Phenyl-2,4-Isodithiobiuret (BPPTB) in Presence of Stannous Chloride

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Platinum and rhodium are extracted with 4-S-benzyl-1-parachlorophenyl-5-phenyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret (BPPTB) in chloroform in the presence of stannous chloride. The procedures are suggested for separation of copper, palladium, platinum and rhodium in the mixtures. Moreover, the binary mixtures of these metals are extracted with BPPTB in chloroform and estimated simultaneously using simple equations.

DESHMUKH and Kharat¹⁻⁴ have shown that 4-S-benzyl-1-parachlorophenyl-5-phenyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret (BPPTB) is a potential analytical reagent for determination of Pd(II), Rh(III) and Cu(II).

Pd(II) and Cu(II) can be separated by extraction with BPPTB using isoamyl alcohol and chloroform. Pd(II), Pt(IV) and Rh(III) present in a mixture are separated and estimated spectrophotometrically. Moreover, the binary mixtures of Pd(II)+Pt(IV), Pd(II)+Rh(III), Pd(II)+Cu(II) and Pt(IV)+Rh(III) are extracted with BPPTB in chloroform and estimated simultaneously using simple equations.

Experimental

Solutions of palladium perchlorate and copper perchlorate in perchloric acid and of platinumic acid ($H_2PtCl_6 \cdot xH_2O$) and rhodium trichloride in hydrochloric acid were prepared and standardised by known methods^{5,7}. The reagent, BPPTB was synthesized according to the reported method⁶ and was purified by repeated crystallization from ethanol. Fresh solution of BPPTB in alcohol-free chloroform⁸ was used. 1.0M stock solution of stannous chloride in hydrochloric acid was used.

Apparatus :

Spectrophotometric measurements were made with Beckman DU-2 spectrophotometer with matched quartz cells with 10 mm light path. Absorbances were noted against a processed reagent solution in chloroform. The pH adjustments of the aqueous solutions were made with an ELICO pH-meter model LI-10 with a glass and saturated calomel electrodes assembly.

Results and Discussion

Absorption spectra of Pd(II) and Cu(II) complexes in the presence of stannous chloride :

A 10 ml solution containing Pd(II) (12.77 μ g) or Cu(II) (7.62 μ g) and 0.1 M stannous chloride at 0.6 M HCl was extracted with 1.0×10^{-3} M BPPTB in 10 ml chloroform. The separated organic layer was scanned on spectrophotometer. The coloured complexes of Pd(II) and Cu(II) show strong absorbances at 390 and 400 nm respectively (Figs. 1 and 2) and hence all the absorbance measurements were carried out at these wavelengths. The molar absorptivities of the coloured complexes of BPPTB with Pd(II) and Cu(II) extracted in chloroform at 390 and 400 nm are 5.08×10^4 and 5.50×10^4 cm^2 mole⁻¹ respectively.

Fig. 1. The spectra of BPPTB and its complex with Pd(II) (in presence of $SnCl_2$)
BPPTB [Pd] = 12.77 μ g
Pd(II)-BPPTB [BPPTB] = 1.0×10^{-3} M

Fig 2. The spectra of BPPTB and its complex with Cu(II) (in presence of SnCl_2)
 BPPTB $[\text{Cu}] = 7.62 \mu\text{g}$
 Cu(II)-BPPTB $[\text{BPPTB}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$

Time for extraction :

Equal volumes of two phases (10 ml) were equilibrated at different times varying from 0.5 min to 30 min. It is observed that the quantitative extraction of Pd(II) and Cu(II) is possible with the agitation of 1 and 5 min respectively. A time of five min was arbitrarily chosen for the entire extraction studies.

Effect of solvents :

Various non-aqueous solvents like benzene, toluene, chloroform etc were tried for the extraction of Pd(II) and Cu(II) with BPPTB. It is found that chloroform is the most efficient solvent for the extraction of these metals in the presence of stannous chloride.

Effect of acid and BPPTB concentration :

The dependence of extraction of Pd(II) and Cu(II) on acidity was investigated by preparing a series of solutions at different acidities (0.1-8.0 M) each containing 12.77 μg of Pd(II) or 7.62 μg of Cu(II) in 10 ml volume. The solutions were extracted with BPPTB solutions of different concentrations in 10 ml chloroform.

It is found that the extent of extraction remains constant at $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ BPPTB for Pd(II) or at $7.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ BPPTB for Cu(II) within the range of 0.3-1.3 M HCl (in the case of Pd) or 0.4-1.0M (in the case of Cu).

Effect of metal ion concentration :

The concentration of each metal ion was varied in the range of $1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ to $1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ in

aqueous layer at 0.1 M stannous chloride and 0.6 M HCl. The aqueous layer was extracted with $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ BPPTB in chloroform. A constancy is observed in distribution ratio in both the cases.

Effect of ionic strength :

The distribution of Pd(II) and Cu(II) was studied at various concentrations of sodium chloride (0.1-5.0 M) at different acidities. It is observed that the magnitude of extraction remains constant upto 2.0M NaCl. However, the extraction decreases above 2.0M NaCl.

Effect of stannous chloride concentration :

Keeping the acid concentration of aqueous layer constant (0.6M), the concentration of SnCl_2 was varied within the range 0.002 M and 0.7 M to study its effect on the extraction of Pd(II) and Cu(II). It is noticed that at about 0.01 M SnCl_2 concentration the absorbance of the organic phase attains a maxima. Higher concentration of stannous chloride has no effect on the colour density of the organic layer.

Stability of the colour of the complex :

The absorbances of coloured complexes of Pd(II) and Cu(II) with BPPTB in chloroform were measured at elapsed intervals of time. The absorbances of Pd(II)-BPPTB and Cu(II)-BPPTB system are found to be constant for 4 and 2 hours respectively.

Adherence to Beer's law :

Samples containing different amounts of metal (0.5-20.0 μg) at 0.6 M HCl at 0.1 M SnCl_2 in 10 ml volume were agitated with $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ BPPTB solution in 10 ml chloroform for 5 min. The organic layers were separated and measured at respective wavelengths of maxima against the similarly processed reagent solution as a blank. It is observed that the yellow complexes of Pd(II) and Cu(II) adhere to Beer's law in the range 0.2-2.0 and 0.1-1.4 μg metal per ml of chloroform at 390 and 400 nm respectively. Ranges suitable for analytical work were determined according to Ringbom plots, and are found to be 0.2-1.6 and 0.2-1.2 μg metal per ml chloroform for Pd(II) and Cu(II) respectively.

Precision and accuracy :

The absorbance of solution each containing 12.77 μg Pd(II) or 7.62 μg Cu(II) from fifteen determinations at their respective wavelengths of maxima were found 0.610 ± 0.010 and 0.600 ± 0.010 respectively. The respective mean deviation are 2.67% and 2.15% for Pd(II) and Cu(II). The respective values for standard deviations are 0.003 and 0.004.

Thus, the methods suggested for the extraction and spectrophotometric determinations are simple, sensitive and fast. Entire operation takes only 30 min.

Separation and estimation of Pd(II) and Cu(II) :

A mixture containing Pd(II) (10-100 μg) and Cu(II) (2-30 μg) was adjusted to pH 0.5 in 10 ml and was extracted with $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ BPPTB in isoamyl alcohol for 10 min. The organic layer was separated and was measured at 355 nm against the similarly processed reagent solution as a blank¹. The aqueous solution was adjusted to pH 4.2 with sodium hydroxide and was extracted with $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ BPPTB in chloroform. The chloroform layer was separated and measured at 368 nm against the similarly processed reagent as a blank². Table 1 indicates the results for some of the mixtures separated.

TABLE 1—SEPARATION AND DETERMINATION OF Pd(II) AND Cu(II)

Amount of Metal taken in μg		Amount of Metal found in μg		% Error	
Pd(II)	Cu(II)	Pd(II)	Cu(II)	Pd(II)	Cu(II)
10.64	2.54	10.70	2.60	± 0.56	± 1.97
21.28	6.35	20.80	6.12	-2.26	-3.62
42.56	12.70	41.63	12.24	-2.19	-3.62
63.84	19.06	63.18	18.42	-1.08	-3.36
85.12	25.40	84.18	25.76	-1.12	-1.02
106.40	31.08	107.20	31.38	± 0.75	+0.97

It is seen from Table 1 that Pd(II) and Cu(II) can be separated quantitatively by solvent extraction employing BPPTB as a reagent.

Separation of Pd(II), Pt(IV) and Rh(III) :

An aliquot containing Pd(II) (10-100 μg), Pt(IV) (20-100 μg) and Rh(III) (10-50 μg) was adjusted to pH 0.5 and was extracted with BPPTB in isoamyl alcohol. Pd(II) content was estimated as described earlier. The aqueous layer was made 3.5 M in HCl and 0.1 M SnCl₂. It was extracted with $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ BPPTB in 10 ml chloroform for 5 min. The separated organic layer was measured

at 407 nm⁵. The residual aqueous layer was made 1.6 M HCl acid and 0.1 M SnCl₂ and was heated in water bath at 90° for one hr. After cooling, the aqueous phase was agitated with $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ BPPTB in 10 ml chloroform and the amount extracted was determined from the calibration curve at 375 nm⁴. Complete removal of Rh(III) from aqueous phase was achieved by three batch extractions. The results obtained for some synthesis mixtures are reported in Table 2, which show that BPPTB can be employed for separation and quantitative determination of these metals within the experimental errors.

Simultaneous determination of Pd(II), Pt(IV), Rh(III) and Cu(II) in binary mixtures :

It is observed that at 1.0 M HCl and 0.1 M SnCl₂ concentration, 100% Pd(II) gets extracted whereas at this condition 67.0 \pm 1.2% Pt(IV) and 65.0 \pm 1.0% Rh(III) are extracted^{3,4}. At 1.7 M HCl and 0.1 M SnCl₂ concentration 71.2 \pm 1.0% Rh(III) and 80.0 \pm 1.2% Pt(IV) are extracted with $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ BPPTB in chloroform^{3,4}. The quantitative extraction of Cu(II) and Pd(II) is possible at 0.6M HCl and 0.1M SnCl₂ with BPPTB in chloroform. These observations are utilised for the determination of these metals.

Pd(II) and Pt(IV) : A mixture containing 5-20 μg Pd(II) and 20-110 μg Pt(IV) was adjusted to 1.0 M HCl and 0.1 M SnCl₂ and was extracted with $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ BPPTB in chloroform and measured at 390 and 407 nm against the processed reagent solution as a blank.

If A_{390} and A_{407} are the absorbance values of chloroform layer at 390 and 407 nm respectively, then,

$$A_{390} = \epsilon_{390}^{\text{Pd}} \cdot [\text{Pd}] + \epsilon_{390}^{\text{Pt}} \cdot [\text{Pt}] \quad \dots \quad (\text{I})$$

and

$$A_{407} = \epsilon_{407}^{\text{Pd}} \cdot [\text{Pd}] + \epsilon_{407}^{\text{Pt}} \cdot [\text{Pt}] \quad \dots \quad (\text{II})$$

where, bracket indicates the concentration of the enclosed metal complex and ϵ the extinction coefficient of the superscribed metal complex at sub-scribed wavelength. The values for $\epsilon_{390}^{\text{Pd}}$, $\epsilon_{390}^{\text{Pt}}$,

TABLE 2—SEPARATION AND DETERMINATION OF Pd(II), Pt(IV) AND Rh(III)

Amount of Metal taken in μg			Amount of Metal found in μg			% Error		
Pd(II)	Pt(IV)	Rh(III)	Pd(II)	Pt(IV)	Rh(III)	Pd(II)	Pt(IV)	Rh(III)
10.64	21.88	10.14	10.27	22.38	9.68	-3.48	+2.06	-4.54
21.28	43.76	20.28	20.68	44.08	19.52	-2.82	+0.73	-3.75
31.92	65.64	30.42	30.91	66.56	28.87	-3.16	+1.40	-5.10
42.56	87.52	40.56	41.63	88.25	38.91	-2.19	+0.83	-4.07
53.20	109.40	50.70	52.03	110.30	48.38	-2.20	+0.82	-4.58
63.84	21.88	50.70	60.48	23.30	49.30	-5.26	+6.49	-2.76
74.48	43.76	40.56	70.55	44.75	38.91	-5.28	+2.26	-4.07
85.12	65.64	30.42	80.52	67.21	27.97	-5.40	+2.39	-8.05
95.56	87.52	20.28	90.57	89.25	19.38	-5.22	+1.98	-4.44
106.40	109.40	10.14	104.00	116.60	9.88	-2.26	+2.01	-2.56

ϵ_{407}^{Pd} and ϵ_{407}^{Pt} at the experimental conditions (1.0 M HCl, 0.1 M SnCl₂, % E_{Pd}=100, % E_{Pt}=67) were found to be 5.08×10^4 , 7.73×10^2 , 2.72×10^{10} and 9.80×10^8 respectively. Therefore, the equations (III) and (IV) can be obtained as the solutions of equation (I) and (II).

$$[Pd] \times 10^5 = 2.0620 \times A_{390} - 0.1626 \times A_{407} \quad \text{(III)}$$

and

$$[Pt] \times 10^4 = 1.0689 \times A_{407} - 0.6144 \times A_{390} \quad \text{(IV)}$$

From these equations (III and IV) the quantity of metal present in the mixture were computed and the results are recorded in Table 3. It is observed from Table 3 that Pd(II) and Pt(IV) can easily be determined in the mixture within the experimental errors.

TABLE 3—SIMULTANEOUS DETERMINATION OF Pd(II) AND Pt(IV)

[HCl]=1.0M; [SnCl₂]=0.1M; [BPPTB]=1.0×10⁻³M

Quantity of Metal taken in μg		Quantity of Metal found in μg		%Error	
Pd(II)	Pt(IV)	Pd(II)	Pt(IV)	Pd(II)	Pt(IV)
5.32	65.64	5.35	60.45	+0.56	-7.91
7.45	43.76	7.53	43.60	+1.07	-0.37
10.64	21.88	11.20	20.08	+5.26	-0.91
12.77	21.88	12.19	22.80	-4.54	+4.20
15.96	109.40	15.15	110.04	-5.08	+0.59
17.02	87.52	16.82	88.59	-1.18	+1.22
21.28	43.76	20.80	42.83	-2.26	-2.58

Pd(II) and Rh(III): A mixture of Pd(II) (5-20 μg) and Rh(III) (10-50 μg) at 1.0 M HCl and 0.1 M SnCl₂ was heated to 90° in water bath for 60 min. After cooling it was extracted with 1.0×10^{-3} M BPPTB in 10 ml chloroform. The separated organic layer was measured at 375 and 390 nm as usual. Then we have

$$A_{375} = \epsilon_{375}^{Pd} \cdot [Pd] + \epsilon_{375}^{Rh} \cdot [Rh] \quad \text{(V)}$$

and

$$A_{390} = \epsilon_{390}^{Pd} \cdot [Pd] + \epsilon_{390}^{Rh} \cdot [Rh] \quad \text{(VI)}$$

where the symbols have their usual meaning. The values of ϵ_{375}^{Pd} , ϵ_{375}^{Rh} , ϵ_{390}^{Pd} and ϵ_{390}^{Rh} at the experimental conditions (1.0 M HCl, 0.1 M SnCl₂, % E_{Pd}=100, % E_{Rh}=65) were 1.56×10^4 , 1.11×10^4 , 5.08×10^4 and 6.82×10^8 respectively. The equations (VII) and (VIII) were obtained as the solutions of simultaneous equation (V) and (VI):

$$[Pd] \times 10^5 = 2.4256 \times A_{390} - 1.4908 \times A_{375} \quad \text{(VII)}$$

and

$$[Rh] \times 10^4 = 1.1101 \times A_{375} - 0.3409 \times A_{390} \quad \text{(VIII)}$$

Thus, the metal contents in mixture have been calculated from these equations and the results are incorporated in Table 4.

TABLE 4—SIMULTANEOUS DETERMINATION OF Pd(II) AND Rh(III)

[HCl]=1.0M; [SnCl₂]=0.1M; [BPPTB]=1.0×10⁻³M

Quantity of Metal taken in μg		Quantity of Metal found in μg		%Error	
Pd(II)	Rh(III)	Pd(II)	Rh(III)	Pd(II)	Rh(III)
5.32	50.70	5.36	51.28	+0.75	+1.14
7.45	20.28	7.25	19.82	-2.68	-2.27
10.64	10.14	10.72	10.02	+0.75	-1.18
12.77	30.42	12.17	29.25	-4.70	-3.85
15.96	30.42	15.04	31.26	-5.76	+2.76
17.02	40.56	16.66	39.48	-2.12	-2.66
21.28	20.28	22.08	19.21	+3.76	-5.28

The results recorded in Table 4 show that Pd(II) and Rh(III) can be determined simultaneously under the given experimental conditions.

Pd(II) and Cu(II): An aliquot containing Pd(II) (5-20 μg) and Cu(II) (5-15 μg) was adjusted to 0.6 M HCl and 0.1 M SnCl₂ in 10 ml volume. It was extracted with 1.0×10^{-3} M BPPTB in 10 ml chloroform. The λ_{max} of BPPTB chelates of Pd(II) (390 nm) and Cu(II) (400 nm) in presence of stannous chloride are not well separated and hence the extract was measured at 380 and 410 nm, the arbitrarily chosen wavelengths against the similarly processed reagent as a blank.

The values for ϵ_{380}^{Pd} , ϵ_{380}^{Cu} , ϵ_{410}^{Pd} and ϵ_{410}^{Cu} at the experimental conditions (0.1 M HCl, 0.1 M SnCl₂, % E_{Pd}=100, % E_{Cu}=100) were 3.50×10^4 , 1.39×10^4 , 2.54×10^4 and 5.08×10^4 respectively. Following equations (IX) and (X) were obtained

$$[Pd] \times 10^5 = 3.5652 \times A_{380} - 0.9755 \times A_{410} \quad \text{(IX)}$$

and

$$[Cu] \times 10^5 = 2.4563 \times A_{410} - 1.7826 \times A_{380} \quad \text{(X)}$$

The results obtained from above equations are inscribed in Table 5, from which it can be concluded that Pd(II) and Cu(II) can be computed simultaneously in the mixture.

TABLE 5 SIMULTANEOUS DETERMINATION OF Pd(II) AND Cu(II)

[HCl]=0.6M; [SnCl₂]=0.1M; [BPPTB]=1.0×10⁻³M

Quantity of Metal taken in μg		Quantity of Metal found in μg		%Error	
Pd(II)	Cu(II)	Pd(II)	Cu(II)	Pd(II)	Cu(II)
5.32	5.08	5.20	5.18	-2.26	+1.97
7.45	6.35	7.68	6.12	+3.09	-3.62
10.64	9.53	10.53	9.21	-1.03	-3.86
12.78	15.64	12.65	15.69	-1.02	+0.97
15.96	12.70	14.90	12.83	-6.64	+1.02
17.02	10.16	16.83	10.33	-1.12	+1.67

Pt(IV) and Rh(III) : A mixture (10 ml) containing Pt(IV) (20-110 μg) and Rh(III) (10-50 μg) at 1.7 M of HCl and 0.1 M SnCl_2 was heated for one hr in water bath at 90°. It was then cooled and extracted with 1.0×10^{-3} M BPPTB in 10 ml chloroform and was measured at 375 and 407 nm as usual.

The values of $\epsilon_{375}^{\text{Rh}}$, $\epsilon_{375}^{\text{Pt}}$, $\epsilon_{407}^{\text{Rh}}$, $\epsilon_{407}^{\text{Pt}}$ at the experimental conditions (1.7 M HCl, 0.1 M SnCl_2 , % $E_{\text{Pt}}=80$, % $E_{\text{Rh}}=71$) were found to be 1.21×10^4 , 0.0, 3.52×10^3 and 1.14×10^4 respectively. The equations :

$$[\text{Rh}] \times 10^4 = 0.8265 \times A_{375} \quad \dots \text{(XI)}$$

and

$$[\text{Pt}] \times 10^4 = 0.8772 \times A_{407} - 0.2552 \times A_{375} \quad \dots \text{(XII)}$$

were obtained and used for the determination of Pt(IV) and Rh(III) in the mixture. The results obtained are reported in Table 6.

TABLE 6—SIMULTANEOUS DETERMINATION OF Pt(IV) AND Rh(III)

[HCl]=1.7M ; [SnCl₂]=0.1M ; [BPPTB]= 1.0×10^{-3} M

Quantity of Metal taken in μg		Quantity of Metal found in μg		% Error	
Pt(IV)	Rh(III)	Pt(IV)	Rh(III)	Pt(IV)	Rh(III)
21.88	10.14	22.20	10.01	+1.46	-1.28
31.88	60.82	22.52	59.31	+2.93	-2.65
43.76	10.14	45.00	10.05	+2.83	-0.89
43.76	20.28	44.08	20.07	+0.73	-1.04
65.64	30.42	66.47	30.21	+1.26	-0.89
87.52	40.56	87.69	39.73	+0.19	-2.05
109.40	50.70	110.03	48.98	+0.58	-3.39

It can be concluded from Table 6 that Pt(IV) and Rh(III) can be determined simultaneously when they are present together in a mixture, without their prior separation.

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